

June, 2023

v.3, n.6, 2023

CSJ **Current**
Scientific Journal

Internationally Indexed Scientific Journal

ISSN 2764-1759

www.currentscientific.com

Current Scientific Journal
v.3, n.6, 2023 - jun. 2023

ISSN 2764-1759

Expediente

Current Scientific Journal
ISSN 2764-1759

www.currentscientific.com

cscientificjournal@gmail.com

Jun/2023
v.3, n.6, 2023

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Periodicidade da publicação: Mensal

Idioma: Aceitos artigos escritos em Português, Inglês ou Espanhol

Idioma de Publicação: Artigos escritos em Inglês ou Espanhol

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 **Current
Scientific Journal** | *Internationally
Indexed Scientific
Journal*

by Grupo MultiAtual Educacional
CNPJ 35.335.163/0001-00
Rua Flauzino Vaz da Silva, nº 211
Bairro Vila São Vicente – Formiga – MG
CEP: 35.574-564
www.grupomultiatual.com.br

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THE RELEVANCE OF ICTs FOR DISTANCE TRAINING OF TEACHERS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8025609

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ABSTRACT

This research seeks to highlight the relevance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) for the distance training of teachers in Brazil. They focus on the treatment of information, articulated with the processes of transmission and communication. ICTs, therefore, multiply the possibilities of research and information for students, who, armed with these new tools, make learning active and become protagonists in the education process. The research was carried out through the bibliographic review method, and as a critical fortune the studies of Trindade (1990), Saraiva (1996), Carmo (1998), Kenski (1998), Tardif (2002), among others. Finally, it can be concluded that ICTs, in the context of distance training of teachers in Brazil, have advantages and disadvantages after their implementation in the classroom, since it is necessary to prepare the educational institution for the use of such digital tools. However, the development of ICTs does not diminish the role of teachers, who now teach students to assess and manage information. In this context, teachers become: organizers of knowledge; providers of learning media and resources; provocative of dialogue, reflection and critical participation.

Keywords : Teacher training. ICTs. Distance education.

INTRODUCTION

This research is the result of a course conclusion work presented to Faculdade Iguazu - FI, as part of the requirements for obtaining the title of Postgraduate in Teaching in Higher Education, under the guidance of Prof. Spec. Udson Leandro Fagundes Dias.

With the recent advances in the teaching-learning process, the use and implementation of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) has become an increasingly latent challenge for the distance training of teachers in Brazil.

Therefore, the main objective of this work is to highlight the relevance of ICTs for the distance training of teachers. This is because they multiply research and information possibilities for teachers, who, equipped with new tools or teaching methodologies, make learning active and become protagonists in the education process.

Specifically, we seek to verify how teacher training is constituted; highlight the relevance of Information and Communication Technologies; and analyze the advantages and disadvantages of Information and Communication Technologies and how they are introduced in teacher education in Brazil.

However, it is important to point out that educational strategies supported by ICTs must gradually be inserted in teaching-learning environments, since one of the biggest challenges for their implementation is, in most cases, the teacher's contact with the information processing, articulated with transmission and communication processes.

The information raised for the construction of the work was obtained through a bibliographical research, and having as critical fortune the studies of Trindade (1990), Saraiva (1996), Carmo (1998), Kenski (1998), Tardif (2002), among others, collecting only theoretical data on the subject under discussion.

In addition, this work deals with the importance of using these tools, considering that they make it possible to reach countless individuals and can be applied to education as a tool for improving the teaching and learning process of the subjects involved.

Concluding this work, the main conclusions obtained in the research are presented, highlighting that ICTs were very important for distance learning to become very popular today.

teacher training

Teacher training is one of the main concerns today, according to Darling-Hammond (2014), since it implies quality, techniques and new teaching methodologies for professionals. Also according to the author,

Inquiry training also helps teachers learn how to look at the world from multiple perspectives, including those of students, whose experiences are very different from the teacher's, and to use this knowledge to develop pedagogies that can reach different learners. Learning to reach students, both the easy to know and the hard to get to, requires crossing borders, the ability to extract

knowledge from others and to understand it when it is offered. (DARLING-HAMMOND, 2014, p. 238-239).

In light of the above, the number of professors has increased, as pointed out by the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research (Inep): “In 2020, there were 366,289 professors working in higher education in Brazil. Of this total, 53.2% were linked to a private HEI and 46.8% to a public HEI” (BRASIL, 2022, p. 31).

The expansion of teacher training, for Litwin (2001), served to outline the most diverse educational plans and for the most intricate situations such as, for example: professional courses, training for the job market or scientific dissemination, literacy campaigns and formal studies at all levels and fields of the educational system.

According to Darling-Hammond (2014), teacher training requires constant searches, especially during the educational process, in a critical and uncompromising way; training, in this case, reflects teaching practice, values teaching knowledge. Relating teaching knowledge and the construction of professional identity, Pimenta (1999) clarifies that:

When students arrive at the initial training course, they already know what it is to be a teacher. The knowledge of their experience of students who were from different teachers throughout their school life. Experience that allows them to say which were the good teachers, which were good in content, but not in didactics, that is, they did not know how to teach. Which teachers were significant in their lives, that is, contributed to their human formation. (PIMENTA, 2008, p. 20).

In other words, teachers are often seen as "mirrors", that is, reflections of those who were their teachers in the past. For example, the subject of class devaluation is something that undergraduate students already know, given that it is something that is always of concern to society (MAUÉS; CAMARGO, 2014).

As Ponte (2000) explains, this assimilation is part of a lengthy process, which involves two distinct aspects: the technological and the educational. Teachers' perspectives on both vary, as some still doubt the convergence of technology and education. Others use them, however, without clearly defined or discussed objectives (TRINDADE, 1990).

As argued by the American philosopher Israel Scheffler (1968),

Teachers cannot restrict their attention to the classroom alone, leaving the broader context and purposes of school education to be determined by others. They must actively take responsibility for the goals to which they have committed themselves and the social context in which those purposes can thrive. If they are not to become mere agents of the state, the military, the media, intellectuals and bureaucrats, they need to determine their own agency

through a critical and ongoing assessment of their purposes, consequences and social context. (SCHEFFLER, 1968, p. 12, our translation).

Given the above, Tardif (2002) classifies teachers' knowledge as temporal, that is, acquired over time, through their experiences. And, when they start working, it is mainly these beliefs that they reactivate to solve their main training challenges:

[...] if we admit that the professionalization movement is, in large part, an attempt to renew the epistemological foundations of the teaching craft, then we must seriously examine the nature of these foundations and extract from them elements that allow us to enter into a reflective and constructive process. critical about our own practices as educators and researchers. (TARDIF, 1999, p. 4).

Thus, the professor is also seen as an opinion maker, with the commitment to formalize the ethics of his students. As a result, the image of the teacher “[...] is, above all, someone who knows something and whose function is to communicate this knowledge to others” (TARDIF, 2002, p. 31). In other words, the author's view is basic: the teacher is primarily responsible for transmitting knowledge, in which this knowledge is sometimes questioned.

Thus, it is commonplace that, during teacher training, there is an “[...] appreciation of mastery of content in specific areas to the detriment of pedagogical subjects” (MASETTO, 2004, p. 134); on the other hand, it is common for the pedagogical disciplines to be devalued, which are often encouraged by teachers of specific disciplines. Another widely disseminated discourse linked to teaching professionals is the one:

[...] which implies building training on reflective, critical, theorizing, analytical professional practice and, therefore, producing professional knowledge, a training project for educators or teachers implies reinforcing professionalism and the adoption of training logics centered on the construction of professional knowledge from, and within, the very practice of the teaching activity. (ROLDÃO et al., 2009, p. 167).

In the discussion pointed out above, the need for constant reflection in teaching work is clear, which is an attitude expected of every teacher when faced with situations of conflict and uncertainty in their initial training, realizing that “[...] reflection is not simply a sequence, but a consequence – an order so consecutive that each idea engenders the next with its natural effect, and at the same time builds on or refers to the predecessor” (DEWEY, 1959, p. 14) .

Therefore, teacher training provides professional improvement for higher education. In addition, the teaching training process offers opportunities and spaces for systematic reflection, productive exchange and collective construction in order to ensure the improvement of teaching knowledge in all its dimensions, respecting its specificity and plurality.

Information and Communication Technologies: advantages and disadvantages

The teacher, with an eye on the use of Information and Communication Technologies for their training, makes room for improvement at all times, because they learn and discover how they reproduce this knowledge, finding new ways to achieve the character of teaching and learning (KENSKI, 2003). On the other hand, the teacher must be careful that the use of ICTs does not replace other activities, as well as for other pieces of knowledge; but that they are a complement for the teacher (SARAIVA, 1996).

According to Klein (2009), for example, ICTs are essential for a new way of thinking and producing knowledge. In other words, “ The challenge posed to Brazilian education concerns all levels, all modalities, all its actors: it is the challenge of quality, modernity, commitment to the History of each one of us and of all as a nation (NEVES, 2009, 25).

Still according to Neves (2009), ICTs are not restricted to investments in physical and technological infrastructure. Implementing this new pedagogical architecture also requires

[...] a broad and articulated set of actions that also include investments (1) in professionals from schools and education systems – to master languages and technologies; (2) in workshops and discussions organized to establish working principles and policies, adequacy of pedagogical projects and evaluation; (3) in curriculum review, design and technological strategies of the courses; (4) in computerized management and logistics systems, among others. (NEVES, 2009, 25).

As ICTs evolve, obstacles to their implementation increase. For Giroux (1997) and Klein (2009), if the teacher does not update himself, the difficulties in his teaching-learning process increase, because the tools are constantly improved for the training of distance teachers and that there is understanding by part of them.

Given this, it is possible to observe that there are strategies and resources in the case of teacher training, especially for knowledge and learning; however, both need to have the theoretical and practical part to occur in its entirety, making it meaningful and satisfactory. (MOORE; KEARSLEY, 2007).

According to Kenski (2003), the use of ICTs in the training of distance teachers not only allows them to be challenged to build new didactic strategies with methods, but also to mediate their own knowledge to meet new technologies.

Moore and Kearsley (2007) describe, in addition to these considerations, that the teacher will also allow the construction of a differentiated and quality educational practice. However, such scores will only be possible after modifications in initial teacher training and in their

pedagogical action, that is, from the evaluation of traditional forms of teaching and adapting them to the social, cultural, political and economic demands of today's society.

Still according to the authors, it also implies the creation of conditions for the appropriation of concepts, skills and attitudes, which gain meaning while the contents addressed are related to the pedagogical objectives and the social, cultural and professional context of their students (MOORE ; KEARSLEY, 2007).

Thus, conditions must be created so that teachers know how to contextualize learning and the experience lived during their training in their reality: the needs of their students and the pedagogical objectives they seek to achieve.

According to Carmo (1998), the implementation of programs for the universalization of ICTs in distance teacher training has been respectable, but it is not enough to just set up rooms with modern computers and Internet access without teachers trained to use them.

Thus, for Carmo (1998), based on these understandings, the teacher committed to the educational processes, through constant updates, becomes a conscious protagonist of the pedagogical work, in addition to resorting to different resources and methodologies to strengthen the processes of teaching and learning.

According to Giroux (1997), teachers should be involved in the production of curricular materials appropriate to the cultural and social contexts in which they teach. According to him, it is necessary to rethink and restructure the nature of the teaching activity and face them as transforming intellectuals (GIROUX, 1997).

It is worth noting that there is resistance from certain teachers regarding the use of ICTs in their training, as stated by Almeida (2000) Araújo (2005) and Antônio (2011), there is poor training and information regarding computer handling, time organization, planning in carrying out the proposed activities, being all a reason for distance learning to be possible.

Carmo (1998), as far as he is concerned, says that the unpreparedness of professors in most higher education courses is, in many cases, due to organization and lack of familiarity with the computer. This is because, for Neves,

Educational leaders should allocate investments to the continuing education of teachers and, also, of the directors themselves and the technical support staff and support for the classroom; for the physical space and furniture that prepare the school to be an institution that educates with technologies; for the acquisition, maintenance and permanent updating of equipment, software, network, connection and consumables, among others. (Neves, 2009, p. 24).

According to Antônio (2011), distance education was individualized and caused insecurity in teachers who are in the process of training, and came to be considered a shallow

class, without foundations; just a way to circumvent traditional and pedagogical methods. However, as time went by, it showed itself to be in another way: human.

In these brief reflections on what ICT means, it is clear that the emphasis is not on machines, but on people. With this, the construction of knowledge and the concern with the teacher have due relevance; educators are not enslaved by machines, nor belittled by students' dexterity. On the contrary, they are valued as professionals. The student's space is important and distinguished by its protagonism, interaction and autonomy to create, learn and innovate.

In view of these considerations, we can infer that in teacher education, in whole or in part, using the use of ICTs as a parameter, it scared, impacted, but brought questions about what was actually apprehended, how this learning was carried out. Thus, Information and Communication Technologies allow the individual to have access to a wide range of information and complexities of a context (near or distant) that, in an educational process, can serve as a learning element, as a socialization space, generating knowledge and scientific knowledge.

Educational technologies

The use of ICTs in the teaching-learning process of distance teachers has, in its advantages and disadvantages, several factors that must be considered essential for its evolution. As Araújo (2005) explains:

The value of technology in education is derived entirely from its application. Knowing how to direct the use of the Internet in the classroom should be an activity of responsibility, as it requires the teacher to value, within a progressive perspective, the construction of knowledge, in order to contemplate the development of cognitive skills that instigate the student to reflect and understand, as they access, store, manipulate and analyze the information they probe on the Internet. (ARAÚJO, 2005, p. 23-24).

In light of the above, it is possible to observe that knowing how to use the internet in the classroom, as it is a very strong means of communication, requires responsibility. On the other hand, it is also necessary to balance this knowledge despite the precariousness found in the contexts in which it needs to happen.

The introduction of ICTs in the training of distance teachers can be an improvement for the teaching-learning issue, as they generate positive and negative results, as they are developed in the learning process, as they can be used as an object of friction.

In this way, ICTs can be combined with teaching practice, as they offer the teacher numerous paths for innovative educational work. Moran addresses this issue very well when he states that,

From the methodological point of view, the educator needs to learn to balance processes of organization and “provocation” in the classroom. One of the fundamental dimensions of the act of educating is to help find a logic within the chaos of information we have, to organize it in a coherent synthesis, even if momentary, to understand it. To understand is to organize, systematize, compare, evaluate, contextualize. A second pedagogical dimension seeks to question this understanding, create a tension to overcome it, to modify it, to advance towards new syntheses, other moments and forms of understanding. For this, the teacher needs to question, create productive tensions and provoke the existing level of understanding (MORAN, 2007, p. 101-111).

Ponte (2000, p. 6-7) problematizes the integration of ICTs in school and argues that, in addition to questioning the relationship between these technologies, they need certain points to be achieved:

- I. The school's objectives;
- II. The forms of learning;
- III. It is necessary to question the school with another type of question;
- IV. How do ICTs change the nature of the educational objectives pursued by the school?
- V. How do the relationships between students and knowledge change?
- VI. How do relationships between students and teachers change?
- VII. How do they change the way teachers live their profession?
- VIII. Does information require a new Pedagogy or not?

As for changing the nature of educational objectives, it is up to higher education institutions and teachers to adapt ICTs to the educational objective, open spaces in the classroom, since they are auxiliary materials in the teaching process (ANTÔNIO, 2011).

Moreover, all these questions raised by Ponte (2000) must be reflected before the moment of lesson planning, or at the time of teacher training. For that,

One of the solutions to this impasse lies in the possibility of educators also participating in the production teams of these new educational technologies. For this, teacher training courses need to be concerned with guaranteeing these new skills. That alongside scientific knowledge and pedagogical knowledge, the teacher be offered the conditions to be an agent, producer, operator and critic of these new educations mediated by electronic communication and information technologies. (KENSKI, 2003, p. 49-50).

For each questioning, there are paths and competent authors, who are able to point out the various links between distance teaching and training, even so some problems need to be overcome, to achieve the desired result in distance teacher training (SARAIVA, 1996) .

Some teaching programs considered of low quality are prowling as disadvantages in distance education for teachers, due to lack of baseless research, citations of authors, research on methodologies and strategies in conventional pedagogical didactic resources, as the materials are constructed by professionals who are not of the area.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Based on what was exposed throughout this work, we conclude that ICTs in distance education depend, above all, on the general process of teacher training in Brazil, which has advantages and disadvantages when it comes to educational technologies. This is because the teacher must be familiar with these technologies. In these cases, we have several types of trainers: those who master digital tools and are able to show their students how to use them in the classroom, those who dominate but do not pass on their knowledge, and those who do not master and ignore these practices.

In other words, we do not intend to exclude pedagogical practices that have proven to be effective and innovative, but rather to make ICTs tools that facilitate learning and articulation in the classroom. Thus, this articulation will serve as another means of facilitating learning and articulation in the classroom, as well as a means of facilitating teacher training.

As we move forward, much prejudice remains in relation to ICTs, as a result of these being used in different ways, to the point of no longer being a learning tool and observed as learning or aid in the process of teaching knowledge.

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